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Geospatial Assessment Of Urban Heat Island In Warri, Delta State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The detrimental effects associated with anthropogenic air pollution have raised concerns globally. Thus, the geospatial assessment of urban heat in Warri was examined. The data used for this study were generated from Thermal Remote Sensing satellite sensors. For the purpose of this research, the Landsat satellite data of 2018, 2020 and 2022 in the study area were obtained as base data for analysis. A spectrometer that measures the reflection of sunlight by the Earth's atmosphere known as Sentinel-5P equipped with the TROPOMI instrument was used to detect and quantify various atmospheric gases. Google Earth Engine was used to extract Carbon dioxide, Methane, Nitrogen dioxide and Sulphur dioxide. The results obtained from the study showed that the concentration value of 4403.34ppm for CO₂ was fair as the mean concentration value was within 2,000-5,000ppm. The CH₄ value for Warri was 90.46ppm which is far below the threshold value of 1000ppm with no health implication. However, NO₂ concentration value within the study area was 582.01ppm. This is far above the unhealthiest range of 201 to 300 as revealed by the air quality index thereby making resident exposed to varying concentration values of NO₂ that could exhibit human health challenges. With the mean SO₂ being 201.82ppb, the ambient air quality for SO₂ in Warri was considered poor. The study therefore recommends the planting of vegetation around buildings (green design), making modifications in the design and orientation of buildings amongst others.

Keywords: anthropogenic air pollution, atmospheric gases, urban heat

1. INTRODUCTION

Urbanization is an extreme example of human land use modification which, does not only radically alter the physical properties of the earth's surface but also affect the thermal, radiative and aerodynamic character of the surface (Oke, 1987). United Nations [UN], (2010) reported that more than half of the world's population resides in the urban areas. Since such a high proportion of the World's population reside in urban areas, it is important to understand the processes determining urban climates and how both past and future urbanization patterns might affect climate at the local and regional scale.

In both industrialized and developing countries, urbanization trend constitutes new millennium challenges amongst which is thermal heat stress resulting from climate change. During the hot season, the Niger-

delta's hot humid tropical environment is characterized with high intensity of solar radiation and low wind velocity. Urban heat island effect and plant destruction amongst other environmental damages has no doubt resulted from the rapid development activities taking place within the past decades. City dwellers are experiencing continuous problems of heat stress due to the recent climate change phenomenon, thus the problem of thermal comfort in urban quarters needs to be addressed. Vegetation is an essential element of urban space planning, though benefits derived from its application include amelioration of urban microclimate through sunlight interception, shading, and control of wind velocity, as well as air purification by absorption and control of noise pollution (Yu and Hien, 2006). Thermal comfort within acceptable standards for urban dwellers living in the city could be aimed at by reducing solar heat and increasing and controlling wind direction as part of planning strategies.

According to Owen, (2009), people living in cities consume less energy compared to people living in suburbs, thus reducing the negative effects of environmental issues for human health and quality of life to pursue sustainable development is mandatory. Perini and Magliocco (2014) stated that vegetation increases the oxygen and moisture in the air, absorbs sun's radiation, gives shade, cools the surrounding environment and generally improves the microclimate of a given area. According to Thomson *et al.*, (2004), thermal conditions are influenced by buildings, surface conditions, open space obstacles and tree canopies causing climate from very hot to cool in the hot season. Therefore, considering the psychological issues and thermal variations, microclimate guidelines should be studied. This will in turn help to develop planning strategies in order to ensure outdoor human comfort in future urban design. Chandler (2001) categorized climate into various levels, which include macroclimate and microclimate. Macroclimate climate is obtained by using data from a number of standardized sites over a large area such as country, continent, and oceans. On the other hand, microclimate includes large areas with fairly uniform conditions which are influenced by air masses moving over earth surface within parameters that characterize a localized area with a geographic scale between 1sqm -100sqm. Surface temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, solar radiation and precipitation are considered as the main factors that modify microclimate.

The urban surfaces (e.g. concretes, pavements and roads) absorb heat and increase the temperature comparatively to the surrounding rural areas. An elevated urban temperature, known as urban heat island reduces human comfort, increases energy consumption in buildings and consequently leads to global warming. Temperatures for large cities like Lagos metropolis have been observed to be significantly increasing for the past three decades. In recent times, research has also showed the effectiveness of urban heat island in changing the urban microclimate which could result to changes of intensity and frequency of rainfall as observed by Noorazuan (2007). One of the most obvious examples of human modification of the earth's surface is urban area. Although, Lamptey *et al.* (2005) and Shepherd (2005) asserted that urban areas cover only 1.2 percent of the earth's surface, it was estimated that in 2003 about 48 percent of the world's population resided in urban settlements and by 2030 it is expected that 61 percent of the world's population will be living in urban areas (UN, 2004).

Basically, there are two main ways to evaluate the UHI phenomenon: conventional weather station automatic temperature measurements (Tzavali *et al.*, 2015) or the Land Surface Temperature (LST) measurements given by Thermal InfraRed (TIR) remote sensing data (Weng, 2002; Voogt, 2003; Mushore *et al.*, 2017; Jiménez-Muñoz *et al.*, 2014; Cristobal *et al.*, 2018). Many authors have investigated the relation between satellite measured LST and other variables such as vegetation cover, land surface albedo, the urban spatial structure and its reflective patterns (Roth *et al.*, 1993; Gallo *et al.*, 1993; Bonafoni *et al.*, 2017; Lo *et al.*, 1997; Chen *et al.*, 2006; Grover *et al.*, 2015 and the review article: Voogt *et al.*, 2003). Also wind speed affected by the urban texture (Yang *et al.*, 2016), and the presence of water bodies have the ability to affect land temperatures (Moyer *et al.*, 2017). Howard in 1810 studied the phenomenon of Urban Heat Island in an area of land that experiences consistent surges in surface temperature more than adjoining areas (Surawar and Kotharkar, 2017). Trends in global migration indicate a predisposition for urban areas because in an absolute short time as of 2018, the urban-based global population had surpassed 50% and it is expected to be at peak at 68 percent by 2050 (UN, 2018).. The impact of UHI is felt across every sphere of human endeavour especially in urban design and

planning, health, comfort, energy management and air pollution amongst others in urban areas. The occurrence of UHI raises peak energy demand and energy consumption by obviously increasing energy demand for cooling systems which indicates a 0.6^oC increase in the ambient air temperatures, electricity requirement for cooling increases by 1.5-2.0 percent at temperatures higher than 20^oC implying that 5.0-10.0 percent of the municipal demand for electricity goes into UHI compensation (Akbari and Konopacki, 2005). Other feasible impacts of UHI observed by Rinkesh (2019) include a sudden increase in air pollutants and greenhouse gases emissions, thermal pollution in the aquatic systems, discomfort, health risks, and local climate alterations such as wind and rainfall patterns, humidity, fog formation and impaired water quality.

The sudden rise in the form of UHI and its attendant challenges as affirmed by Phelan, et al., (2015) include air pollution, heat wave, greenhouse effect and increased energy consumption has been a source of concern to researchers recently. High concentrations of gases and particulates such as CO₂, CH₄ and hydrocarbons pollute the atmosphere, posing risks to both the environment and human health (Ediagbonya et al., 2015). Hence, effective control measures are crucial to address air pollution, which has become a significant environmental concern in the modern era. Vehicle emissions, generator fumes, and building site are stated as the significant sources of urban air pollution in Nigeria (Mopa et al., 2020). Recent studies on ambient air pollutants in Nigeria found higher concentrations of the frequent air pollutants in Lagos State, Ibadan, Kano, Kaduna, Port Harcourt, and the Niger Delta region (Abulude et al., 2021; Daful et al., 2020; Obisesan and Weli, 2019). In addition, such cities also constitute significantly higher PM levels than the World Health Organization's (WHO) hourly average standards (Abulude et al., 2021). It is difficult to assess the continuous spatiotemporal profile of air pollutants since most urban areas throughout the world lack comprehensive air quality monitoring networks (Rudke et al., 2023). In addition, the utilization of remote sensing to analyze the air quality of many developing African nations is a necessity where in-situ ground monitoring stations are limited (David-Okoro et al., 2020; Marais et al., 2014). While in-situ monitoring stations are commonly used to collect data on surface air pollution concentrations, this data is typically point-based rather than spatially continuous. It is observed that most pollutants are found in metropolitan environments and thus might be challenging to detect their geographic features using in-situ measurement techniques (Filonchuk et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2018). As an alternative, satellite imagery offers the benefit of delivering geographically consistent information over extensive areas (Fernandes et al., 2019). It could play a crucial role in evaluating atmospheric trace gases (Lim et al., 2009). Anejionu et al. (2015) and Marais et al. (2014) also have utilized satellite data to detect air pollution in Nigerian cities. However, the environment in Nigeria is degrading and there are inadequate monitoring stations, and environmental legislation is less acknowledged (Adeniran et al., 2019). Therefore, the geospatial assessment of urban heat in the study area is paramount.

Aim and Objectives of Study

This study is aimed at evaluating the geospatial assessment of urban heat in Warri with the following objectives:

- i. To determine the extent of urbanization from 1992-2022 of Warri in Delta State.
- ii. To evaluate the microclimatic elements in the study area.
- iii. To determine the impacts of the evaluated microclimatic elements on the environment.

Hypotheses

- i. There is no relationship between impact of urbanization on microclimatic elements and the environment.
- ii. There is no relationship between microclimatic elements and human health.

Study Area

Delta state covers a landmass of about 18,050 km² (6,970m²), of which more than 60% is land. The state lies approximately between 5°00' and 6°45' E and 5°00' and 6°30' (Ebewore, 2020). It is geographically located in Nigeria's Midwest, bounded in the north and west by Edo state, the east by Anambra, Imo, and Rivers states, southeast by Bayelsa state (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2021) and on the southern extreme is the Bight of Benin, which covers about 160km of the state's coastline. There are various seasons in Nigeria and its meteorological parameters vary from one location to another (Abaje and Oladipo, 2019).

The issue of seasonal variation in Nigeria cannot be over-stretched. Delta state is generally low-lying without any remarkable hills. The state has a wide coastal belt inter-laced with rivulets and streams, which form part of the Niger Delta (Alabi, 2017). The 2006 National Population and Housing Census put the population of Delta state and Warri with a population of 4,112,445 and 149,603 people respectively (NPC, 2006). The climatic condition of experiences moderate rainfall and moderate humidity for most part of the year. The climate is equatorial and is marked by two distinct seasons: the dry season and the rainy season. The dry season lasts from about November to April and is significantly marked by the cool "harmattan" dusty haze from the north-east winds. The rainy season spans May to October with a brief dry spell in August, but it frequently rains even in the dry season. The area is characterized by tropical equatorial climate with mean annual temperature of 32.8°C and annual rainfall amount of 2673.8mm. There are high temperatures of 20°C and 29.6°C. The natural vegetation is of rainforest with swamp forest in some areas. The forest is rich in timber trees, palm trees, as well as fruit trees.

Warri being formally the divisional headquarter for Shell Petroleum Development Co-operations (SPDC), is also a swamp location for exploration and production of oil for SPDC. Other oil companies as well as oil servicing companies are also situated in the town. Major industries in the area are oil mining, oil servicing, petro-chemicals and sculptural and bronze making establishments. Others include commerce, tourism, etc.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data Types and Sources

The type of data used in the course of this study included:

2.1.1 Administrative map sourced for from office of surveyor general of Delta State.

2.1.2 Microclimate Satellite Remote Sensing based sensors:

i. Satellite images: Thermal Remote Sensing satellite sensors are designed to offer surface temperature and emissivity information from land and sea surface from several spacecraft sensors, including Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER), and Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR), in addition to raw Landsat thermal data. For the purpose of this research Landsat collection was sourced for and used. Landsat has the longest history of Earth Observation among the available Earth Observing Satellites, it started operations July 23, 1972 and expired, January 6, 1978, but the project has continued to improve itself with several follow-ups to Landsat 9 and afterwards is Landsat Next due in the year 2030, while Landsat 6 missed orbits. The epochs of interest were 2003, 2013 and 2023. Landsat Imagery; Landsat ETM+ for 2003 (USGS, 2023), Landsat ETM+ for 2013, and Landsat OLI for 2023 with Path 189 and Row 56 is determined by converting the Latitude and longitude from the USGS website (<https://landsat.usgs.gov/wrs-2-pathrow-latitude-longitude-converter>) of the study area based on Worldwide Reference System 2, or using KML/KMZ or shapefile (<https://www.usgs.gov/media/files/landsat-wrs-2-scene-boundaries-kml-file>), which can be loaded into Google Earth or any software that support shapefile respectively from necessary and available repositories.

Image analysis: The Landsat satellite data of 2018, 2020 and 2022 (a period of 2years interval) of the study area (Warri) was obtained as base data for analysis. The choice of these years was based on availability, consistency and reliability of data. The images were classified using supervised classification techniques. After the initial image processing and rectification, the images were enhanced in order to enable visual interpretation and better comprehend the tonal presentations, the nature, types and characteristics of the land use discernable from the images. Land use classification scheme was developed by careful modification of the Handerson classification scheme with particular reference to the peculiar characteristics of the study area. The refined land- use classification scheme was used as the input in the selection of the training sites that were used in the supervised classification using Erdas Imagery. With the aid of head on digitizer the classified image will be vectorised and the map for each year period will then be captured.

ii) Microclimatic element (Temperature) maps from 2003-2023 (a period of 20 years) of Warri was obtained. For air pollution or air quality monitoring over the study area, Sentinel-5P was considered for this research although it has less history of data collection in reference to other EOS, but with great resources in the recent times with better capability and capacity onboard the platform to determine aerosol, air quality/pollution parameters. Sentinel-5P (also known as Sentinel-5 Precursor) is a European Space Agency (ESA) Earth observation satellite launched in 2017. Its main mission is to monitor air pollution and track the transport of pollutants in the atmosphere. Sentinel-5P is equipped with the TROPOMI (TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument) instrument, which is a spectrometer that measures the reflection of sunlight by the Earth's atmosphere. This allows it to detect and quantify various atmospheric gases, such as: Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), Ozone (O₃), Carbon monoxide (CO), Methane (CH₄), and Sulfur dioxide (SO₂). The data collected by Sentinel-5P is used for various applications, including air quality monitoring, climate modeling, weather forecasting, emission inventory creation and research and development of new atmospheric models. Sentinel-5P is a precursor to the Sentinel-5 mission, which is part of the European Space Agency (ESA's) Copernicus program. The Copernicus program aims to provide accurate and timely data and information services for Earth observation, climate change, and environmental monitoring.

2.1.3 Hardware and Software required for the research included;

1. Computer System and related accessories like mouse, printers
2. Internet
3. Microsoft excel for processing of field coordinates.
4. ARCGIS 10.8.2 software for digitizing the administrative map and image digital number conversion to temperature using Landsat ETM + band 4 and 5, Landsat 7 and 8, OLI band 10 and 11.
5. Google Earth Engine to extract Carbon dioxide, Sulphur dioxide, Methane and Nitrogen dioxide (see Appendix 1 for the code)
6. Microsoft word for presentation of report
7. GPS for field coordinates.

2.2 Method of Data Analysis

Data obtained was analyzed using inferential statistical techniques. The inferential statistics, which included correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship between the impact of urbanization on environmental microclimatic elements and also if there is any relationship between microclimatic elements and human health in the study area.

2.2.1 Calculation of Urban Heat Island (UHI)

In other to generate the temperature for the study area, the impact of urban growth on surface temperature was examined. The essence of this was to reveal the microclimate changes over the reference period in the surface temperature from the study area as the built-up area keep on expanding. Then, the impact of the urban growth on surface temperature was assessed graphically and numerically. This is to confirm that the urban growth was the major factor that create the concept of urban heat island. In order to achieve this, the sequence of data processing is highlighted below:

Step 1: Conversion to Top of Atmospheric Radiance (ToAR)

$$L_i = M_L Q_{CAL} + A_L$$

where:

L_i = ToAR spectral radiance (watts/(m²*srad*mm))

M_L = Band-specific multiplicative rescaling factor from the metadata (RADIANCE_MULT_BAND_x, where x is the band number)

Q_{CAL} = Quantized and calibration standard product pixel values (DN)

A_L = Band-specific additive rescaling factor from the metadata

Step 2: Conversion to Top of Atmosphere Brightness Temperature

$$TB = \frac{ks}{\left(\frac{k1}{L\lambda} + 1\right)} - 273.15$$

T = Top of atmosphere brightness temperature (K)

L_l = TOA spectral radiance (watts/(m²*srad*mm))

$K1$ = Band-specific thermal conversion constant from the metadata ($K1_CONSTANT_BAND_x$, where z is the thermal band number)

$K2$ = Band-specific thermal conversion constant from the metadata ($K2_CONSTANT_BAND_x$, where x is the thermal band number)

Step 3: Calculating Emissivity

e = emissivity

$$e = 0.004 * Pv + 0.986$$

$$Pv = ((NDVI - NDVI_{min}) / (NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min}))^2$$

Step 4: conversion from At-Satellite Temperature to Land Surface Temperature

$$T = TB / (1 + (l * TB / c^2) * \ln(e))$$

l = wavelength of emitted radiance (center wavelength of thermal band)

$$c^2 = h * c / s = 1.4388 * 10^{-2} \text{ mK} = 14388 \text{ mK}$$

$$h = \text{Planck's constant} = 6.626 * 10^{-34} \text{ Js}$$

$$s = \text{Boltzman constant} = 1.38 * 10^{23} \text{ J/K}$$

$$c = \text{velocity of light} = 2.998 * 10^2 \text{ m/s}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DETERMINATION OF URBAN STATUS FOR WARRI BETWEEN 1992 AND 2022

The built up area growth within this region seems small based on economic activities from 7.88 km² in 1992 to 9.75 km² in 2022 (Table 3.1 and Figure 3.1), the compactness of development was observed and the water body/river around this settlement at the southern and eastern part hindered the growth.

Table 3.1: Built up Area Between 1992 and 2022 in the Study Area

Settlement	1992		2022	
	Area (km ²)	Area (Hec)	Area (km ²)	Area (Hec)
Warri	7.88	787.83	9.75	974.64

Source: Author's Lab analysis

Fig 3.1: Urban Status of Warri in 1992

Fig. 3.2: Urban Status of Warri in 2022

3.2 Spatio-Temporal Analyses Of The Microclimatic Elements In The Study Area

The value of CO₂ in Warri was 4789.58ppm in 2018 (Table 3.2 and Figure 3.3). This value decreased to 4422.32ppm in 2020 (Table 3.2 and Figure 3.4) and further reduced to 3998.41ppm in 2022 (Table 3.2 and Figure 3.5). The rate of reduction was 367.29ppm and 423.91ppm from 2018 to 2020 and from 2020 to 2022 respectively. The reduction in the concentration of CO₂ might be due to the vegetation covers that flank the banks of rivers and stream that are common in Warri and its connected towns like Agbarho, Usubi, Ugbomro and Ogbolokposo that could influence the CO₂ concentration. With a mean concentration of CO₂ of 4403.34ppm (Table 3.2) recorded in Warri, the ambient air quality could be said to be fair (Table 3.3), with the consequences of headaches, fatigue, stagnant, stuffiness, poor concentration, loss of focus, increased heart rate, nausea on the inhabitants.

Table 3.2: Mean concentration of Carbon dioxide in the Study Area

Settlement	CO ₂ Value in ppm			Mean
	2018	2020	2022	
Warri	4789.58	4422.32	3998.41	4403.34

Source: Author's analysis

Table 3.3: Ambient Air Quality for Carbon Dioxide

Air Quality Category	Concentration (ppm)	Percentage by volume (%)	Description of indoor air quality
Excellent	400	0.04	Normal outdoor air
Very Good	400-1,000	0.04-0.1	Typical CO ₂ levels found indoors
Good	1,000-2,000	0.1-0.2	Common complaints of drowsiness or poor air quality
Fair	2,000-5,000	0.2-0.5%	Headaches, fatigue, stagnant, stuffiness, poor concentration, loss of focus, increased heart rate, nausea
Poor	> 50,000	> 5%	Toxicity due to oxygen deprivation occurs
Extremely poor	> 100,000	> 10%	Oxygen deprivation in seconds: convulsions, coma, and death

Source: <https://www.co2meter.com/blogs/news/carbondioxideindoorlevelschart>

Fig 3.3: Carbon dioxide Concentration in the Study Area in 2018

Fig 3.5: Carbon dioxide Concentration in the Study Area in 2022

3.2.2 Concentration of Methane in Warri

The value of CH₄ concentration in Warri was 263.88ppm in 2018 (Table 3.4 and Figure 3.6). This value decreased by 106.27ppm to 157.61ppm in 2020 (Table 3.4 and Figure 3.7) and further decreased by 67.15ppm to 90.46ppm in 2022 (Table 3.4 and Figure 3.8). The mean Methane value for Warri was 90.46ppm; this is far below the threshold value of 1000ppm (Table 3.5). The low concentration of methane in Warri could be due to the reduced activities and non-existence of some of the anthropogenic emission sources such as landfills, agricultural activities, oil and gas natural systems, coal mining, stationary and mobile combustion, wastewater treatment and some industrial processes that are either non existing or at low level of operation in Warri.

Table 3.4: Mean concentration of Methane in the Study Area

Settlement	2018	2020	2022	Mean
Warri	263.88	157.01	90.46	170.45

Source: Author’s analysis

Table 3.5: Ambient Air Quality for Methane

Exposure level (ppm)	Effect or symptom
1000	NIOSH 8-hours TLV*
50,000 to 150,000	Potentially explosive
500,000	Asphyxiation

* TLV = Threshold Limit Value

Source: Alberta Agriculture, food and rural development

Table 3.6: Mean concentration of Methane in the Study Area

Settlement	2018 (ppm)	2020 (ppm)	2022 (ppm)	Mean (ppm)
Warri	557.77	547.43	640.84	582.01

Source: Author’s analysis

Table 3.7: Air Quality Guide for Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂)

Concentration (ppm)	Air Quality Index	Description of indoor air quality
0 -50	Good	No health impacts are expected when air quality is in this range
51 – 100	Moderate	Individuals who are unusually sensitive to nitrogen dioxide should consider limiting prolonged outdoor exertion
101 – 150	Unhealthy for Sensitive Groups	The following groups should limit prolonged outdoor exertion: I. people with long disease such as asthmatics ii. Children and adults
151 – 200	Unhealthy	The following groups should limit prolonged outdoor exertion: I. people with long disease such as asthmatics ii. Children and adults Everyone else should limit prolonged outdoor exertion
201 – 300	Very Unhealthy	The following groups should limit prolonged outdoor exertion: ii people with long disease such as asthmatics ii. Children and adults Everyone else should limit prolonged outdoor exertion

Fig 3.6: Methane Concentration in the Study Area in 2018

Fig 3.7: Methane Concentration in the Study Area in 2020

Fig 3.8: Methane Concentration in the Study Area in 2022

3.2.3 Concentration of Nitrogen dioxide in Warri

The value of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) concentration in Warri was 557.77ppm in 2018 (Table 3.6 and Figure 3.9). This value decreased by 10.34ppm to 547.43ppm in 2020 (Table 3.6 and Figure 3.10), and increased by 93.41ppm to 640.84ppm in 2022 (Table 3.6 and Figure 3.11). The increased nitrogen dioxide concentration in Warri could be traced to increase in vehicular use in Warri and off road equipment such as power plants and construction heavy-duty trucks. With a mean concentration of 582.01ppm of nitrogen dioxide in Warri, which is far above the unhealthiest range of 201 to 300, the following groups should limit prolonged outdoor exertion: i people with lung disease such as asthmatics, ii. children and adults and everyone else should limit prolonged outdoor exertion (Table 3.7).

Fig 3.9: Nitrogen dioxide Concentration in the Study Area in 2018

Fig 3.10: Nitrogen dioxide Concentration in the Study Area in 2020

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